

Original Article

ENCOURAGING FEMALE ENTREPRENEURS IN UTILIZING THEIR ENTREPRENEURSHIP POTENTIALS FOR POVERTY ALLIVATION IN ENUGU NORTH LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF ENUGU STATE

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Abstract

The main purpose of the study was to determine the strategies for encouraging female entrepreneurs in utilizing their entrepreneurship potentials for poverty alleviation in rural communities in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State. The study was guided by two research questions and two null hypotheses. A survey research design was adopted for the study. The population comprised 186 registered and practicing female entrepreneurs operating in rural communities in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State. There was no sampling due to the manageable size of the population. The instrument used for data collection was a 17 item structured questionnaire grouped into two sections according to the research questions that guided the study. The items were structured in four point rating scale. The instrument was validated by experts two from Business and Entrepreneurship Education Department and one from Measurement and Evaluation unit of Mathematics and Computer Education Department, all from Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu and the reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha which yielded 0.73. Out of 186 copies distributed, 171 copies were returned giving 91.93% return rate. Mean, standard deviation and t-test statistics were the statistical tools used for data analysis. Based on the data analysis, the study identified the strategies for encouraging female entrepreneurs in utilizing their entrepreneurship potentials for poverty alleviation in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State. One of the major findings of the study is the lack of financial capital as well as high tax rates faced by female entrepreneurs. Based on the findings of the study, recommendations were made among which include; that the government should provide an enabling environment that would encourage women entrepreneurs in utilizing their entrepreneurship potentials for poverty alleviation and non-governmental bodies should increase efforts in imparting positive strategies like, giving them grant, loan, security and others as identified in the study to encourage female entrepreneurs in utilizing their entrepreneurship potentials for poverty alleviation.

Keyword: Entrepreneurship, Female Entrepreneurs, Poverty Alleviation.

Original Article

Introduction

The increasing level of unemployment, poverty, youths' reactivity, government inability to pay workers and non-payment of retirement benefits have set the need to promote entrepreneurship development. This condition has led the higher institution to incorporate employability and creativity skills as component of entrepreneurship development programmes into their curriculum. This was aimed to provide potential students with desirable learning experiences culminating into productive knowledge, skills and attitude identification opportunities within their environment (Mbah and Onoh, 2016). The central focus is to achieve the desired result through effective entrepreneurial skill development of individuals for economic independence. Entrepreneurship according to Onoh (2015) is the act of identifying business opportunity and utilizing available human and material resources in order to achieve success in it. Entrepreneurship is regarded as a process of exploring the opportunities in the market place and arranging resources required in exploiting and assuming the risks to make profit. Mbah and Onoh (2016) stated that, entrepreneurship is the ability to identify a business opportunity and undertake risk in order to harvest such opportunity for economic development.

Poverty alleviation could be achieved through the promotion of micro and macro enterprises established by entrepreneurs including female entrepreneurs. Idoko (2012) observed that entrepreneurs are job creators, employers of labour and major contributors to national economic growth and world over. There is need to encourage female entrepreneurs to utilize their entrepreneurship potentials for poverty alleviation. Entrepreneurship is not just an academic concept but a way of life because entrepreneurship involves the ability to set up a business enterprise as different from being employed. It therefore depicts that entrepreneurship is one of the keys to self-

employment, sustainable economic growth, poverty alleviation and rural development.

In contemporary society, entrepreneurial activities could be carried out by both men and women in urban and rural areas to become self-employed and economically independent. Zaid and Popoola (2010) in Ubah (2022) indicated that the challenges of rural areas are multifaceted phenomenon determined by the cumulative and interactive impacts of numerous and varied factors like housing, infrastructure, access to various amenities, income and standard environment. Rural areas usually lack government attention, provision of amenities and government presence that would attract development. This necessitated the need for study to ascertain the contribution of women entrepreneurs in poverty alleviation.

According to Agbionu, Agbionu, Ikon and Chinwe (2015) women entrepreneurship is seen to attract considerable amount of attention as a subject of academic debate in its own light. The authors posit that such interests are mainly on the fact that female entrepreneurs are now considered important forces in economic growth and development of their nations which is the crux of poverty alleviation.

Female entrepreneurs are women who take part in entrepreneurial activities either in full time or part time, small scale or large scale or even in a multinational environment. In line with the above, Agbionu, Olulana, and Agbodike, (2018) affirmed that female entrepreneurs are simply women that participate in total entrepreneurial activities, who take risks involved in combining resources together in a unique way to take advantage of the opportunities identified in their immediate environments through the production of goods and services. The experience of the female entrepreneurs would be considered in determining the strategies for encouraging female entrepreneurs for poverty alleviation. The more experienced female entrepreneurs are the people who have five years and above experience while below

five years could be less experienced. Their experiences are necessary in managing entrepreneurial activities for poverty alleviation. This no doubt hinges on the fact that women have been and are still agents of poverty alleviation.

Poverty alleviation on its own is a process aimed at reducing the incidence of poverty in any environment (Ubah, 2022), continued that most developed and developing countries of the world have at one time or another felt the impact of poverty. Poverty means a condition of inadequate fundamental freedom of action and choice that the better-off take for granted. Women in many countries of the world have been forced by one circumstance or another to engage in alternative avenues of generating an income with a greater number of women setting up businesses to balance work and family commitments. This is seen in a study by Agbionu, Agbionu, Ikon and Chinwe (2015) that women in businesses are a growing force in the economy and in transition environments.

In the opinion of Nwokike and Orga (2017), women entrepreneur may be seen as group of women who initiate, organize and operate a business enterprise. Stanley Leonel 1992 cited by Nwokike and Orga (2017), defined women entrepreneurs as confident, innovative and creative women capable of achieving self-economic independent, individually or in collaboration, grantees employment opportunities for others through initiative, establishing and manning the enterprise by keeping pace with her personal, family and social life.

The contributions of women in poverty alleviation can be noticeable in the following areas: Agriculture, Social Network, Workforce, Educating the young ones and in healthcare (Nwokike and Orga 2017). Deducing from the contributions of women in material development and poverty alleviation in rural communities, the researchers are of the opinion that there should be appropriate strategies to encourage

women entrepreneurs for poverty alleviation in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State.

Strategy is a plan of action designed to achieve a long-term or overall aim. Time to develop a coherent economic strategy. A strategy describes how the ends (goals) will be achieved by the means (resources). Strategy can be intended or can emerge as a pattern of activity as the organization adapts to its environment or competes. It involves activities such as strategic planning and strategic thinking. The contributions of women in the economic growth and development as well as poverty alleviation around the world calls for attention from government at all levels, non-governmental organization and other stake holders to assist women to realize these goals, but it has not been so in some parts of the world especially in the developing world like Nigeria. Government provisions such as loan, grants, facilities, favourable policy and training could influence women participation in economic growth and poverty alleviation.

Mbah and Imakwu (2017) stated that the non-governmental organizations have role to play through sensitization, training and provision of financial support services. Observation shows that women entrepreneurs in Enugu North Local Government Area needs encouragement from both Government and non-governmental organizations so that they can fully utilize their potentials in poverty alleviation.

Enugu North is one of the 17 local government Areas in Enugu State. Observation equally shows that there are lots of female entrepreneurs in Enugu North and if they can be adequately motivated and encouraged, they can even go a long way to alleviate poverty in their communities.

Statement of Problem

There is a rising problem of underemployment and unemployment resulting to poverty and all forms of social ills in the Nigerian society. This problem may emanate from lack of entrepreneurial skills and

competencies by individuals. The changing trends in the socio-economic environment have given rise to many unplanned changes in the life style and occupation of individuals (including women) in the rural communities. Traditionally, it is believed that women are created to play supportive roles in family life. They are usually engaged in cooking, home management and children upbringing. The men in those days were seen fending for the family in the areas of building houses, paying children's school fees, providing financial assistance for huge expenses in the family. In those times again, it was only the man that engage in paid employment while the women were home keepers. But due to changes in socio-economic and cultural environments, women no longer play only supportive roles alone as they are involved in paid and self-employment.

In spite of all these remarkable reports on women and entrepreneurship, the reality of this relationship in many societies and transition economies is that female entrepreneurs consistently struggle and remain dormant without remarkable output due mainly to poor support from government and other relevant stakeholders. The promotion of women activities then in Nigeria remained disappointing and their contribution overlooked as a result of the systematic neglect as a whole. Their contributions in different economic activities are clear and unambiguous which necessitated the need to support women entrepreneurship and productive activities.

Although women have recently received more recognition for their entrepreneurial efforts, many still feel neglected by the government, lack financial support, receive little help from non-governmental organizations and their communities, and face other challenges that prevent them from reaching their full potential. This may likely result to increase in the level of poverty in Enugu North Local Government Area, which may result to hunger, sickness, high death rate, kidnapping, robbery and other social vices.

The researchers are worried by this ugly situation especially in relation with women entrepreneurs in Enugu North where women entrepreneurship needs to be supported in order to alleviate poverty. This situation need to be addressed in order to support women entrepreneurship and promote the family and general economic conditions. It is against this background that, the researcher sought to determine the strategies for encouraging female entrepreneurs for Poverty Alleviation in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enug State.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of this study was to determine the strategies for encouraging female entrepreneurs in utilizing their entrepreneurship potentials for poverty alleviation in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State. Specifically, the study sought to determine the:

1. government related strategies for encouraging female entrepreneurs in utilizing their entrepreneurship potentials for poverty alleviation in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State.
2. non-governmental related strategies for encouraging female entrepreneurs in utilizing their entrepreneurship potentials for poverty alleviation in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study;

1. What are the government related strategies for encouraging female entrepreneurs in utilizing their entrepreneurship potentials for poverty alleviation in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State?
2. What are the non-governmental related strategies for encouraging female entrepreneurs in utilizing their entrepreneurship potentials for poverty alleviation in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State?

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significant.

H0₁ There is no significant difference between the mean scores of experienced and less experienced female entrepreneurs on the government related strategies for encouraging female entrepreneurs in utilizing their entrepreneurship potentials for poverty alleviation in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State.

H0₂ There is no significant difference between the mean scores of experienced and less experienced female entrepreneurs on the non-governmental related strategies for encouraging female entrepreneurs in utilizing their entrepreneurship potentials for poverty alleviation in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State.

Method

This study adopted a survey research design. According to Nworgu (2015) survey research design is one in which a group of people or items are studied by collecting and analyzing data from only a few of them to represent the entire group. This design was suitable for the study because the researchers collected data from registered female entrepreneurs in Enugu North Local Government Area on the government and non-governmental organizations on strategies for encouraging female entrepreneurs in utilizing their entrepreneurship potentials for poverty alleviation. The area of the study was Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State, Nigeria. The population comprised 186 registered female entrepreneurs operating in rural communities in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State. The population was determined from field survey conducted by the researchers on micro and small-scale businesses owned and managed by female entrepreneurs. The number was manageable and as such, there was no sampling.

The data collection was carried out using 17 item structured questionnaire developed by the researchers based on the related literature. The instrument was structured in four-point response options of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) with numerical values of 4, 3, 2 and 1. The instrument was validated by three experts, two from the Department of Business and Entrepreneurship Education and one from Mathematics and Computer Education Department, measurement and evaluation option all from Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu. Their corrections and suggestions after the validation were used to produce the final instrument used for the study. The instrument was trial tested using 20 female entrepreneurs from Enugu South Local Government Area of Enugu State who were not part of the population under study. The reliability coefficient yielded .73 using Crombach Alpha method. This .73 coefficient is in-line with Uzoagulu (2013) that reliability index of 0.60 to 1 shows that the instrument is highly reliable.

Two research assistants were used in the administration of the questionnaire and out of 186 copies distributed 171 copies were returned giving 91.93% return rate. Weighted means and standard deviations were used to answer the research questions. Decisions on the research questions were made using the lower and upper limits of the mean based on a four point rating scale. The standard deviation was used to determine the homogeneity or otherwise of the opinions of the respondents. The t-test was used to test the null hypotheses. The analysis was carried out using Statistical Packages Social Science (SPSS). The significant value (at 2-tail) was compared with .05 level of significant at the appropriate degree of freedom. The null hypothesis was not rejected where the significant value was less than the .05 level of significance and at appropriate

degree of freedom; otherwise the null hypothesis was rejected.

Results

The results of the study are presented according to the research questions and hypotheses that guided the study.

Research Question 1

Table 1: Respondents’ mean scores on the governmental strategies for encouraging female entrepreneurs in utilizing their entrepreneurship potentials for poverty alleviation in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State

S/N	The following are the government related:	More Experienced N= 78		Less Experienced N= 93		Overall		Decision
		X ₁	SD ₁	X ₂	SD ₂	X _G	SD _G	
		1	Provision of loan to support women entrepreneurship	3.52	0.56	3.56	0.55	
2	Government encourage female entrepreneurs with low tax/rates	3.15	0.74	3.16	0.73	3.15	0.73	Agree
3	Provision of zero interest loan	2.98	0.75	2.96	0.75	2.97	0.75	Agree
4	Supporting women entrepreneurs with grants	2.99	0.77	2.99	0.76	2.99	0.77	Agree
5	Making policies that would encourage women to engage in entrepreneurial ventures	3.00	0.62	3.02	0.61	3.01	0.62	Agree
6	Providing social amenities to facilitate growth of small scale businesses	3.05	0.58	3.04	0.59	3.05	0.58	Agree
7	Educating women entrepreneurs on best practices for entrepreneurial businesses through seminar/workshop	2.92	0.79	2.93	0.79	2.92	0.79	Agree
8	Providing supervisory guidance to young female entrepreneurs on investment windows	2.95	0.85	2.95	0.86	2.95	0.85	Agree
9	Providing security to women entrepreneurs in rural areas	3.01	0.79	3.06	0.78	3.03	0.79	Agree
Cluster Mean/SD		3.06	0.72	3.07	0.71	3.07	0.71	Agree

Note: X = Mean; SD =Standard Deviation

The analysis of data presented in Table 1 shows that the mean scores range from 2.92 – 3.54. Provision of loan to support female entrepreneurs. (Educating women entrepreneurs on best practices for entrepreneurial success). The overall mean of 3.07 shows that the identified items are the various ways government can encourage female entrepreneurs to utilize their potentials for poverty alleviation in Enugu state. The cluster low standard deviation of .71 indicates that the respondents have relatively similar opinion on the itemized governmental influence of female entrepreneurs for poverty alleviation in rural communities.

HO₁

There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of experience and less experience female entrepreneurs on the governmental influence of female entrepreneurs for poverty alleviation in rural communities in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State.

Table 2: Summary of t-test analysis of mean scores of experienced and less experienced female entrepreneurs on the governmental influence of female entrepreneurs for poverty alleviation in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State

Variables	N	T	df	Sig. (2tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Decision
More Experienced	78	0.267	32	0.717	0.14423	0.86312	NS
Less Experienced	93						

NS= Not Significant

The result of t-test analysis in Table 2 shows that the t-value at .05 level of significance and 169 degree of freedom for the items is .267 with a significant value of .717. Since the significant value of .717 is more than the .05 level of significance the null hypothesis is not significant. This means that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of experienced and less experienced female entrepreneurs on the governmental influence of female entrepreneurs for poverty alleviation in rural communities in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State.

Research Question 2

What are the non-governmental related strategies for encouraging female entrepreneurs for poverty alleviation in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State?

Table 3: Mean scores and standard deviation on the non-governmental related strategies for encouraging female entrepreneurs for poverty alleviation in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State

S/N	The non-governmental organization influence of female entrepreneurs for poverty alleviation in rural communities includes;	More Experience d N= 78		Less Experience d N= 93		Overall		Decision
		X ₁	SD ₁	X ₂	SD ₂	X _G	SD _G	
10	Donation of cash to support women entrepreneurship	3.33	0.65	3.34	0.66	3.34	0.65	Agree
11	Establishing business partnership with the women entrepreneurs for poverty alleviation	2.97	0.81	2.97	0.81	2.97	0.81	Agree
12	Provision of zero interest loan	3.31	0.79	3.09	0.79	3.20	0.79	Agree
13	Supporting women entrepreneurs with grants	2.97	0.76	2.96	0.77	2.97	0.77	Agree
14	Organizing seminars/workshops for women entrepreneurs	3.01	0.76	2.99	0.76	3.00	0.76	Agree
15	Linking female entrepreneurs to creative opportunities	3.08	0.75	3.22	0.76	3.20	0.75	Agree
16	empowerment programmes for rural women on best practices in entrepreneurship	3.02	0.76	3.01	0.77	3.02	0.76	Agree
17	monitoring of young female entrepreneurs on investment windows	3.07	0.73	3.09	0.73	3.08	0.73	Agree
	Cluster Mean/SD	3.10	0.75	3.08	0.76	3.10	0.75	Agree

Note: X = Mean; SD =Standard Deviation;

The data presented in Table 3 indicates that the means score ranges. Provision overall item mean ratings ranges from 2.97 to 3.34 depicting agree. This shows the respondents agree to the items as the non-governmental organization strategies for encouraging female entrepreneurs for poverty alleviation in rural communities in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State. The overall cluster mean score of 3.10 indicates agree. The low standard deviation of .75 shows that the respondent’s opinions is homogenous to the items as non-governmental organization influence of female entrepreneurs for poverty alleviation in rural communities.

HO₂

There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of experience and less experience female entrepreneurs on the non-governmental organization influence of female entrepreneurs for poverty alleviation in rural communities in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State.

Table 4: Summary of t-test analysis of mean score of experienced and less experienced female entrepreneurs on the non-governmental organization influence of female entrepreneurs for poverty alleviation in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State

Variables	N	t	df	Sig. (2tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Decision
More Experienced	78	0.129	169	0.472	0.08513	0.89869	NS
Less Experienced	93						

NS= Not Significant

The result of t-test analysis in Table 4 shows that the t-value at .05 level of significance and 169 degree of freedom for the items is 0.129 with a significant value of .472. As the significant value of 0.472 is more than the 0.05 level of significance the null hypothesis is not significant. This means that there is no significant difference with respect to the items on the mean scores of experience and less experience female entrepreneurs on the non-governmental organization influence of female entrepreneurs for poverty alleviation in rural communities in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State.

Discussion

The findings of the study according to research question one showed that the identified items are the government related strategies for encouraging female entrepreneurs in utilizing their entrepreneurship potentials for poverty alleviation in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State. The government strategies includes; provision of loan to support female entrepreneurs, encouraging female entrepreneurs with low tax/rates, provision of zero interest loan, supporting women entrepreneurs with grants, making policies that would encourage women to engage in entrepreneurial ventures, providing social amenities to facilitate growth of small scale businesses, educating rural women on best practices for entrepreneurial businesses through

seminar/workshop, providing supervisory guidance to young female entrepreneurs on investment windows and providing security to entrepreneurs in rural areas. The findings of the study were in line with Agu (2021) that government needs to develop strategies for building capacity and providing the needed facilities for acquiring entrepreneurial skills, training and retraining for self-employment and poverty alleviation of individuals. The government is a major stakeholder in encouraging women entrepreneurs to contribute meaningfully in job creation, economic development and poverty alleviation. This could equally be achieved through the provision of facilities, policies and platforms that would increase women participation and survival in entrepreneurial development and poverty alleviation in rural communities.

Moreover, the findings of the study indicated that there was no significant difference between the mean scores of experienced and less experienced female entrepreneurs on the governmental influence of female entrepreneurs for poverty alleviation in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State. This showed that experience of the respondents have no significant impact on the identified government related strategies for encouraging women entrepreneurs for poverty alleviation in rural communities.

Furthermore, the findings of the study on research question two revealed that the non-governmental organization could encourage female entrepreneurs for poverty alleviation in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State. The non-governmental organizations could encourage women entrepreneurs for poverty alleviation in the following ways: establishing business partnership with the women entrepreneurs for poverty alleviation, provision of zero interest loan, supporting women entrepreneurs with grants, organizing seminars/workshops for women entrepreneurs, linking female entrepreneurs to creative opportunities, empowerment programmes for rural women on best practices in entrepreneurship and monitoring of young female entrepreneurs on investment windows. The findings of the study were inconsonance with Agbionu, Ibenta and Egbunike (2013) and Mbah and Imakwu (2017) that stated the non-governmental organizations have role to play through sensitization, training and provision of financial support services to rural women entrepreneurs for poverty alleviation in rural communities. Jaiswal (2017) also pointed that non-governmental bodies' involvement and practices, regardless of other stakeholders have been found to influence the growth of female entrepreneurs in job creation, economic development, and poverty alleviation in the society.

In a related development, the findings of the study showed that there is no significant difference in the mean scores of experienced and less experienced female entrepreneurs on the non-governmental organization influence of female entrepreneurs for poverty alleviation in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State. The implication of the findings was that experience of the female entrepreneurs had no significant influence on the identified non-governmental organization influence of female entrepreneurs for poverty alleviation in rural communities in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State.

Conclusion

The study investigated the strategies for encouraging women entrepreneurs in utilizing their entrepreneurship potential for poverty alleviation in rural communities. The study identified the government and non-governmental organizations influence of female entrepreneurs for poverty alleviation in rural communities. The findings of the study indicated that government and non-governmental organizations influence the activities of female entrepreneurs for poverty alleviation in rural communities.

The study therefore concludes that the government and non-governmental organizations influence could be increased to attract more women in entrepreneurship and promote economic development of the rural communities especially Enugu North LGA of Enugu State. Based on the findings, government and non-governmental organizations are expected to increase their efforts in addressing the issues and challenges of entrepreneurship development as it concern women for poverty alleviation.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The government should provide loans to female entrepreneurs to encourage them to utilize their potentials for poverty alleviation in Enugu North Local Government Area..
2. Non-governmental organization should encourage women entrepreneurs by donating cash to them so that they can utilize their potentials for perverty alleviation in Enugu North Local Government Area.

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